

Research on metals recovery from waste produced during lead pyrometallurgical process

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This work presents the research on the recovery of valuable metals (copper, cobalt and nickel) from waste material, originating from the lead pyrometallurgical process. The waste material was characterized in terms of its quantitative and phase composition. The quantitative analysis of the material showed that its chemical composition is as follows (wt%): 39–49 – Fe, 29–31 – As, 10–12 – Cu, 3.7–4 – Co, 2.4–2.9 – Ni, 2.3–3.4 – Pb. In turn, phase analysis showed that all components present in the waste material are in metallic form. Leaching tests were performed, using sulfuric acid solution without and with the addition of oxidants (oxygen gas, 30% hydrogen peroxide solution, 65% nitric acid solution) and hydrochloric acid; at different ratios of the solid phase (waste material) to liquid phase (leaching solution - sulfuric acid solution), for 4 to 6 hours, at the temperature above 90°C. As a result of the research, the most favourable conditions for the leaching process were determined. The leaching process of the waste should be carried out in the 15% sulfuric acid solution with the addition of 65% nitric acid solution at the temperature above 90°C for 4 hours, while the ratio of solid to liquid phase should be 1:10.

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Biography:

Joanna Malarz graduated in 2009 with a master's degree from the Faculty of Mathematics, Physics and Chemistry of the University of Silesia in Katowice. In 2021, she defended her doctoral thesis entitled "Allyl compounds in the synthesis of trisubstituted isoxazolines", Faculty of Science and Technology of the University of Silesia in Katowice. Since 2015, she has been working in the Łukasiewicz Research Network - Institute of Non-Ferrous Metals. She is the author and co-author of 19 publications and 21 patents, and takes part in research and development works, national and European projects, and work commissioned from the industry. Her main interest areas are hydrometallurgy, recovery of strategic metals, especially cobalt, nickel, copper and rhenium.

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